

Twister Generator of Arbitrary Uniform Sequences

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Abstract: Twisting generators for pseudorandom numbers may use a congruential array to simulate stochastic sequences. Typically, the computer program controls the quantity of elements in array to limit the random access memory. This technique may have limitations in situations where the stochastic sequences have an insufficient size for some application tasks, ranging from theoretical mathematics and technic constructions to biological and medical studies. This paper proposes a novel approach to generate complete stochastic sequences which don't need a congruential twisting array. The results of simulation confirm that received random numbers are distributed absolutely uniformly in the set of unique sequences. Moreover, combination of this novel approach with an algorithm of tuning for twisting generation affords the length extension of created sequences without requiring additional computer random access memory.

Key Words: Pseudorandom Number Generator, Stochastic Sequences, Congruential Numbers, Twister Generator

Categories: G.2.1, G.3, F.2

1 Introduction

This article continues previously presented approaches [Deon and Menyaev 2016], where the principle of twisting generation of complete uniformed sequences is discussed. Typical pseudorandom number generators (PRNG) are broadly used in cryptography [Shamir 1983; Lewko and Waters 2009; Claessen and Palka 2013], testing of technical systems [Eichenauer-Herrmann and Niederreiter 1994; Hellekalek 1995; Sussman et al. 2006; Mandal et al. 2016], analyzing of teletraffic [Li 2010, 2017], theoretical simulation of natural processes [Niederreiter 1992; Meka and Zuckerman 2010; Goplan et al. 2011], theoretical mathematics [Leva 1992; Applebaum, 2012; White et al. 2008; Langdon 2009], biological verification studies [Juratly et al. 2015, 2016; Cai et al., 2016; Sarimollaoglu et al., 2014], clinical medicine [Menyaev et al. 2013, 2016; Tong et al. 2014; Chapman et al. 2015; Carey et al. 2016] and development of medical equipment [Zharov et al. 2001; Menyaev and Zharov 2005, 2006; Menyaev and Zharova 2006]. Previously, the length of 15 or 16 bits for numbers from intervals $[0:2^{15}-1] = [0:32767]$ and $[0:2^{16}-1] = [0:65535]$ accordingly was sufficient for random numbers. However, the modern

tasks require the lengths of 32-64 bits for the diapasons of random numbers. Using the technology of twisting generation, which is based on congruential arrays [Matsumoto and Nishimura 1998; Matsumoto et al., 2006, 2007; Bos et al. 2011; Deon and Menyayev 2016] may be faced with limitations in some cases. Let's analyze this more in detail.

To build a twister, a congruential generation is needed. It allows organizing the random value x_{i+1} followed by current value x_i using function $f(x_i)$ limited by modulus m :

$$x_{i+1} = f(x_i) \bmod m. \quad (1)$$

Historically, function $f(x_i)$ linear dependences from the congruential constants a and c :

$$f(x_i) = ax_i + c. \quad (2)$$

In generator MT19937 [Matsumoto and Nishimura 1998] a realization of index i is accomplished by array mt , which could be placed and then initialized in computer RAM by using the following code:

```
#define N 624
static unsigned long mt[N];
static int mti;
mt[0] = seed & 0xffffffff;
for ( mti = 1; mti < N; mti++)
    mt[mti] = ( 69069 * mt[mti-1] ) & 0xffffffff;
```

The elements in array mt include the random numbers created by linear congruential equation (2) with constants $a = 69069$ and $c = 0$. The quality of generated numbers is defined by an orthogonal transformation of matrix A [Matsumoto et al., 2006, 2007]. Now our current interest is directed to the address space, which is required for 624 words having length of 4 bytes or 32 bits (that time type *long* signed 4 bytes, later it became 8 bytes). However, this size may be insufficient to realize some tasks in the address space of $\log_2(624 \cdot 4) = \log_2 2496 < 12$ bits using the common data bus of a computer or microcontroller.

The same approach is used for twisting random numbers with a length of 64 bits [Saito and Matsumoto 2008]. In that variation a congruential generation of an array is applied, and in turn it consists of 312 elements of random numbers.

```
#define NN 312
static unsigned long long mt[NN];
mt[0] = seed;
for (mti=1; mti<NN; mti++)
    mt[mti] = (6364136223846793005ULL * (mt[mti-1] ^ (mt[mti-1] >> 62)) + mti);
```

This 2nd variation has the same address space, i.e. $\log_2(312 \cdot 8) = \log_2 2496 < 12$. Herein, one can see that the global twister of a whole sequence having 2496 bits totally, cannot provide completeness of uniform generation of random numbers. In other words, the initial congruential array has to contain more elements.

In our previous study [Deon and Menyayev 2016] it has been shown that absolute

uniformity of generation is reachable only in complete sequences of random numbers. In that case each complete sequence consists of non-repeatable random numbers having w bit length. The interval of generation is defined by length w of each number $x \in [0:2^w - 1]$. In this interval the global circular twister provides absolute uniformity of generation for the initial congruential array.

```
static public int w = 16;           // number bit length
static public int N = 1 << w;      // sequence length
static public int[] x = new int[N]; // sequence
static public int maskW = (int)(0xFFFFFFFF >> (32 - w));
x[0] = x0;                          // the beginning of sequence
for ( int i = 1; i < N; i++ )
    x[i] = ( a * x[i - 1] + c ) & maskW;
```

In this listing the length of a random number is 16 bits. Therefore, a congruential generation realizes the interval of all the numbers as $x \in [0:2^w - 1] = [0:2^{16} - 1] = [0:65535]$. All of them are presented in array x only once.

While this seems promising, what should be done if the task of generation requires the numbers having accidentally received bit length w ? If the technology of MT19937 is applied for that task, there is no guarantee that all the numbers are created without unpredictable skipping of elements within uniform generation. On the other side, if a technology of complete sets is used, the whole array could not be placed in the RAM of a computer or microcontroller; i.e. if the length of number is 32 bits, the 32-address buses will not have enough space for the computer program due to all available bytes being occupied by the array used for congruential twisting generation. The same story may occur with 64 bit random numbers when 64-address buses are used.

Following this, the aim of the current article is to find the solution for generation of complete sequences having uniformly distributed random numbers in interval $[0:2^w - 1]$ with accidental bit length w , i.e. without congruential-twister array technology.

2 Fundamentals

Let's consider a sequence of numbers with equal bit length w . The initial number is defined as x_0 . All other numbers may be derived using congruential formulas (1) and (2). If the amount of unique non-repeatable numbers is equal 2^w , the sequence is completed due to the fact that it contains all the numbers from interval $[0:2^w - 1]$. It has been confirmed experimentally [Deon and Menyaev 2016], that congruential sequences with 2^w length may have the property of completeness if the constant a is the subject to the condition $(a - 1) \bmod 4 = 0$, and also constant c takes odd values and is the subject to the condition $c \bmod 2 \neq 0$. Both constants a and c do not exceed the interval limited by $[0:2^w - 1]$.

In complete congruential sequences the global circular twister creates complete sequences as well. In addition, it should be taken into account that complete sequences have uniform singular distribution of their elements. This follows directly from the definition of completeness. Therefore, the properties of complete

congruential and twisting sequences are sufficient for the following next constructions. Our goal is to abandon the initial congruential array, but the task of complete congruential twisting generation of uniformly distributed random sequences still has to be fulfilled.

Figure 1: Schematics of generation for the global twister 1 without congruential arrays

Let there be a seed $x_0 \in [1:2^w - 1]$ with a bit mask as $maskW = 0xFFFFFFFF \gg (32 - w)$. Next, let's take into account the pair of adjacent congruential numbers $\langle xL, xR \rangle$ which are placed to the left and to the right. In the beginning, let's define the left value as $xL = x_0$; right value is defined by the congruence $xR = (a \cdot xL + c) \& maskW$. So, the congruential sequence is generated if both operations $xL = xR$ and $xR = (a \cdot xL + c) \& maskW$ are accomplished.

The quantity of iterations is one less than the total quantity of numbers in the sequence due to the initial number coinciding with the beginning of sequence $xL = x_0$. Thus, for generation of congruential twister 0 the working array couldn't be used; the subsequent random value is generated at the next stage of the iteration.

Now let's consider the twister 1, which is by definition a global circular shift to the left of congruential sequence (twister 0), with a step size of 1 bit. The forming of twister 1 for the sequence having $w = 3$ bits is displayed in Fig.1.

The length of the complete sequence is $N = 2^w = 2^3 = 8$. To demonstrate an example, let's use the following values: $x_0 = 1$, $a = 5$, $c = 1$. For this variation the congruential generation creates the sequence 1 6 7 4 5 2 3 0. Based on this, twister 1 provides the following next sequence 3 5 7 1 2 4 6 0, and its elements are presented as xG values in Fig.1. In the initial iteration adjacent congruential numbers are $xL = 1$, $xR = 6$. A simultaneous shift to the left with a step of 1 bit provides $xG = 3$. The 2nd iteration starts from the equating of xR taken from the initial iteration to $xL = xR = 6$. At the same time, the new value of xR is derived as said above: $xR = (a \cdot xL + c) \& maskW = (5 \cdot 6 + 1) \& 111_2 = 7$. The new value of $xG = 5$ is generated similarly as in the initial generation: it is a simultaneous shift to the left of $xL = 6$ and $xR = 7$ with a step of 1 bit. So, after realizing of all 8 iterations the new 8 generated numbers xG for complete twisting sequence will be received.

Below is the program code to realize described twisting technology in which the array of the initial congruential generation with subsequent global circular shift is abandoned. In each new global twister nT the shift of adjacent congruential numbers is made $w - 1$ times in the interval of $nW \in [1:w - 1]$ bits with the mask $maskT$. This program code is organized as the static object class prepared in C# dialect from Microsoft Visual Studio 2013; the similar code may be demonstrated for the language C (dialect Win32) or C++ (dialect CLR). Anyway, the result is the same. The names *P030202* and *cP030202* are chosen by chance.

```
namespace P030202
{ class cP030202
  { static public uint w = 3U;           // number bit length
    static public uint N1 = 0xFFFFFFFF >> (32 - (int)w);
    static public uint x0 = 1U;         // sequence beginning
    static public uint xB = x0;        // current twister beginning
    static public uint xG;              // created random number
    static public uint xL = 0U, xR = x0; // paired numbers
    static public uint a = 5U;          // congruential constant a
    static public uint c = 1U;          // congruential constant c
    static public uint nW = 0U; // paired twister number in w
```

```

static public uint nT = 0U;    // twister number in nwN
static public uint nV = 0U;    // element number in x
static public uint maskW = 0xFFFFFFFF >> (32-(int)w);
static public uint maskU = 1U << ((int)w - 1);    // elder
static public uint maskT = maskU;    // twister first bits
//-----
static void Main(string[] args)
{ uint N = N1 + 1;            // sequence length
  Console.WriteLine("w = {0} N1 = {1} N = {2}",
    w, N1, N);
  Console.WriteLine("a = {0} c = {1}", a, c);
  int k = 1;                  // sequence number
  for (int nT = 0; nT < N; nT++)
  { for (nW = 0; nW < w; nW++)
    { maskT = maskU;          // twister mask beginning
      for (int m = 1; m < nW; m++)
        maskT |= maskU >> m;
      Console.WriteLine("k = {0,3} | ", k++);
      xR = xB;                // sequence beginning
      for (int i = 0; i < N; i++)
      { xL = xR;              // pair left value
        xR = Cong(xL);        // pair right value
        if (nW == 0) xG = xL; // congruential pair
        else xG = TwistPair(); // twister pair
        Console.WriteLine("{0,3}", xG);
      }
      Console.WriteLine(" | nT = {0,2} nW = {1} ",
        nT, nW);
      if (nW == 0) Console.WriteLine();
      else Console.WriteLine("maskT={0:X}", maskT);
    }
    xB = Cong(xB);            // next beginning
  }
  Console.ReadKey();         // result viewing
}
//-----
static uint Cong(uint z)
{ return (a * z + c) & maskW; // next value
}
//-----
static uint TwistPair()
{ uint g = (xR & maskT) >> (int)(w - nW); // elder
  return ((xL << (int)nW) & maskW) | g; // younger
}
//=====
}
}

```

After executing this code the following listing appears.

```

w = 3 N1 = 7 N = 8
a = 5 c = 1
k = 1 | 1 6 7 4 5 2 3 0 | nT=0 nW=0
k = 2 | 3 5 7 1 2 4 6 0 | nT=0 nW=1 maskT=4
k = 3 | 7 3 6 2 5 1 4 0 | nT=0 nW=2 maskT=6
k = 4 | 6 7 4 5 2 3 0 1 | nT=1 nW=0
k = 5 | 5 7 1 2 4 6 0 3 | nT=1 nW=1 maskT=4
k = 6 | 3 6 2 5 1 4 0 7 | nT=1 nW=2 maskT=6
k = 7 | 7 4 5 2 3 0 1 6 | nT=2 nW=0
k = 8 | 7 1 2 4 6 0 3 5 | nT=2 nW=1 maskT=4
k = 9 | 6 2 5 1 4 0 7 3 | nT=2 nW=2 maskT=6
k = 10 | 4 5 2 3 0 1 6 7 | nT=3 nW=0
k = 11 | 1 2 4 6 0 3 5 7 | nT=3 nW=1 maskT=4
k = 12 | 2 5 1 4 0 7 3 6 | nT=3 nW=2 maskT=6
k = 13 | 5 2 3 0 1 6 7 4 | nT=4 nW=0
k = 14 | 2 4 6 0 3 5 7 1 | nT=4 nW=1 maskT=4
k = 15 | 5 1 4 0 7 3 6 2 | nT=4 nW=2 maskT=6
k = 16 | 2 3 0 1 6 7 4 5 | nT=5 nW=0
k = 17 | 4 6 0 3 5 7 1 2 | nT=5 nW=1 maskT=4
k = 18 | 1 4 0 7 3 6 2 5 | nT=5 nW=2 maskT=6
k = 19 | 3 0 1 6 7 4 5 2 | nT=6 nW=0
k = 20 | 6 0 3 5 7 1 2 4 | nT=6 nW=1 maskT=4
k = 21 | 4 0 7 3 6 2 5 1 | nT=6 nW=2 maskT=6
k = 22 | 0 1 6 7 4 5 2 3 | nT=7 nW=0
k = 23 | 0 3 5 7 1 2 4 6 | nT=7 nW=1 maskT=4
k = 24 | 0 7 3 6 2 5 1 4 | nT=7 nW=2 maskT=6

```

This result may be compared with similar studies in a previous simulation [Deon and Menyaev 2016]: they are equal. However, the difference is that in a current program code the algorithm realized in function *Main()* does not use the initial congruential array which is applied in [Matsumoto and Nishimura 1998; Deon and Menyaev 2016]. Thus, the achieved fact is that generation of received complete sequences of random numbers isn't limited by technical options of the computer equipment. The length of the complete sequence may be any size long, however, the bit length w of random numbers may be limited by capabilities of common data bus of 32 or 64 bits used for logical operations in computers.

3 Code States

In the previous section, the simulation technique of the complete sequence uses the generalizing cycles for calculation of random numbers. Practical applications mostly need the technology providing the random value after a single order. To obtain that code let us use the programming technique based on the method of storing state st for generator. The state transition diagram from the current state to the next one is shown in Fig. 2. The assignment is the following:

- state 101 provides the congruential generation of random numbers in complete sequence;
- state 102 allows tuning of parameters for twisting generation;
- state 103 realizes the twisting generation of random numbers in complete sequence;
- state 104 sets the congruential beginning for the next congruential and twisting complete sequence;
- state 105 organizes the ending of generation process for the all possible congruential and twisting complete sequences, and it sets the repeatable beginning state of generator.

Figure 2: Code states for generation of random numbers

Below is the program code which realizes the common generation of random numbers. In the main function *Main()* each random value *uint x* is created independently. All of them together are collected in complete random sequences. Functions *Cong()* and *TwistPair()* are the same as in program *P030202* in previous section *Fundamentals*. The names *P030301* and *cP030301* are chosen by chance.

```

namespace P030301
{ class cP030301
  { static public uint w = 3U;          // number bit length
    static public uint N1 = 0xFFFFFFFF >> (32 - (int)w);
    static public uint x0 = 1U;        // sequence beginning
    static public uint xB = x0;       // current twister beginning
    static public uint xG;            // created random number
    static public uint xL = 0U, xR = x0; // paired numbers
    static public uint a = 5U;        // congruential constant a
    static public uint c = 1U;        // congruential constant c
    static public uint st1 = 101U;    // state of generation of xG
    static public uint nW = 0U;       // paired twister number in w
    static public uint nT = 0U;       // twister number in nwN
    static public uint nV = 0U;       // element number in x
    static public uint maskW = 0xFFFFFFFF >> (32-(int)w);
    static public uint maskU = 1U << ((int)w -1); // elder
    static public uint maskT = maskU; // twister first bits
//-----
    static void Main ( string[] args )
  
```

```

{ uint N = N1 + 1;
  Console.WriteLine ( "w = {0} N = {1}", w, N );
  Console.WriteLine ( "a = {0} c = {1}", a, c );
  for ( int k = 1; k <= w * N; k++)
  { Console.Write ( "k = {0,3} | ", k );
    for ( int i = 0; i < N; i++)
    { uint x = Next (); // random number
      Console.Write ( "{0,3}", x );
    }
    Console.Write ( " | nT = {0,2} nW = {1}",
      nT, nW );
    Console.WriteLine ();
  }
  Console.ReadKey (); // result viewing
}
//-----
static public uint Next ()
{ Next1 (); // random number generation
  return xG; // generated random number
}
//-----
static bool Next1 ()
{ bool FlagNext1 = false; // xG will be created
  bool FlagWhile1 = true; // looking for twister
  while ( FlagWhile1 ) // st1 states running
  { switch ( st1 ) // states switching
    { case 101U: // congruential generation
      xL = xR; // beginning of pair
      xR = Cong ( xL ); // ending of pair
      xG = xL; // generated number
      if ( nV < N1 ) nV++; // next number
      else st1 = 102U;
      FlagWhile1 = false; // number is created
      break;
    case 102U: // preparation to pair twister nW
      nW++; // a pair twister number in w
      if ( nW < w )
      { maskT = maskU; // elder 1 in twister mask
        for ( int m = 1; m < nW; m++)
          maskT |= maskU >> m; // twister mask
        xL = xB; // twister beginning
        xR = Cong( xL ); // pair xL, xR
        nV = 0U; // value number in twister nT
        st1 = 103U; // generate twister nT
      }
      else st1 = 104U;
      break;
    }
  }
}

```

```

case 103U:          // twister generation
  xG = TwistPair (); // result of generation
  xL = xR;          // beginning of the next pair
  xR = Cong ( xL ); // next pair
  if ( nV == N1 ) st1 = 102U;
  else nV++;        // next value number
  FlagWhile1 = false; // number is created
  break;
case 104U: // the end of twisters nW inside nT
  if ( nT < N1 )
  { nT++; // nT number for twister group nW
    xB = Cong( xB ); // beginning
    xR = xB;
    nW = 0U; // twister number in w
    nV = 0U; // value number in twister
    st1 = 101; // generation of twister nT
  }
  else st1 = 105U;
  break;
case 105U: // initial parameters
  nW = 0U;
  nT = 0U;
  xR = x0;
  st1 = 101U; // initial parameters
  break;
} // switch
} // while
return FlagNext1; // result of generation
}
//-----
// functions Cong and TwistPair
//=====
}
}

```

After this code execution the listing below appears; it is presented here with abridgments for what the dash lines are used.

```

w = 3 N = 8
a = 5 c = 1
k = 1 | 1 6 7 4 5 2 3 0
k = 2 | 3 5 7 1 2 4 6 0
k = 3 | 7 3 6 2 5 1 4 0
k = 4 | 6 7 4 5 2 3 0 1
k = 5 | 5 7 1 2 4 6 0 3
k = 6 | 3 6 2 5 1 4 0 7
-----
k = 22 | 0 1 6 7 4 5 2 3

```

k = 23 | 0 3 5 7 1 2 4 6
 k = 24 | 0 7 3 6 2 5 1 4

Complete sequences in the listing are similar with ones which appear after execution of program P030202 in the previous section *Fundamentals*. The only difference is that now each random value is received without using the cycles of transitional twisters.

4 Constructions and results

When creating the twisting sequences an important note should be addressed when choosing parameters a and c which are received in accordance with (2) for generation of random numbers having w bits. Both parameters have to belong to the interval $a, c \in [0: 2^w - 1]$ and have to satisfy the following properties:

$$\begin{cases} (a - 1) \bmod w = 0 \\ c \bmod 2 \neq 0, \quad \text{for odd numbers} \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

The automatic tuning of parameter a satisfying the subinterval $[ab, ae] \subset [0: 2^w - 1]$ may be performed in various ways. In this current work for constant a the algorithm of double interval modeling is applied. The diagram of two subintervals $a1 + a2 = [a1b, a1e] + [a2b, a2e] \subset [0: 2^w - 1]$ is showed in Fig.3.

Figure 3: Schematics of interval realization for congruential constant a

The value $a1e$ is to the left from $N/2$, while value $a2b = a1e + 4$ is to the right from $N/2$. Moving of a in interval $a1$ is accomplished from the right to the left, i.e. from $a1e$ to $a1b$ with a step of -4 ; moving of a in interval $a2$ is accomplished from the left to the right, i.e. from $a2b$ to $a2e$ with a step of $+4$. This choice for a was made artificially to provide better confusion for generation. Congruential parameter c could take all the odd numbers in the interval $[1: 2^w - 1]$ that range from 1 to $2^w - 1$.

In Fig.4 the code states are shown for the random number generation with automatic tuning of congruential constants and masks of twisters. The states starting from 10x are the same as in previous section *Code State*, thus, their description is skipped below. The other assignments are the following:

- state 1 begins the total generation;
- state 2 sets the parameters for block 1 to continue the generation after

congruential constants are changed;

- state 201 provides the changing of constant c ;
- state 202 defines the subintervals $a1$ or $a2$ for constant a ;
- state 203 derives the new value for a in subinterval $a1$;
- state 204 derives the new value for a in subinterval $a2$;
- state 205 ends the total generation and provides transition to state 1.

Figure 4: Code states for tuning of random number generation

Below is the program code for the name space *nsDeonYuliTwist32D* in which dynamic class *cDeonYuliTwist32D* provides twisting generation of random numbers having any length up to 32 bits.

```
namespace nsDeonYuliTwist32D
{ class cDeonYuliTwist32D
  { public uint w = 16U;           // number bit length
    public uint N1 = 0U;          // maximal number
    public uint x0 = 1U;          // sequence beginning
    uint xB = 1U;                 // current twister beginning
    uint xG = 0U;                 // created random number
    uint xL = 0U, xR = 1U;        // paired numbers
    double abf = 0.39;           // relative beginning of a
    double aef = 0.39;           // relative ending of a
    public uint a1b = 1U, a1e = 0U; // interval a1
    uint a1s = 0U;                // state of interval a1
    public uint a2b = 1U, a2e = 0U; // interval a2
```

```

uint a2s = 0U;           // state of interval a2
uint a1 = 5U;           // constant for interval a1
uint a2 = 5U;           // constant for interval a2
uint nA = 1U;           // constant number for a1 or a2
public uint a = 5U;     // current value of constant a
double cbf = 0.1;       // relative beginning of c
double cef = 0.3;       // relative ending of c
public uint cb = 1U, ce = 0U; // interval c
public uint c = 1U;     // congruential constant c
uint stG = 0U;          // state group number
uint st0 = 1U;          // initial state group
uint st1 = 101U;        // xG generation group
uint st2 = 201U;        // parameter change group
public uint nW = 0U;    // pair twister number in w
public uint nT = 0U;    // twister number
public uint nV = 0U;    // element number in x
public uint maskW = 0U; // number mask
public uint maskU = 0U; // elder bit mask
public uint maskT = 0U; // twister bits
//-----
public cDeonYuliTwist32D()
{ N1 = 0xFFFFFFFF >> (32 - (int)w); // max-number
  x0 = N1 / 7; // sequence beginning
}
//-----
public uint Next()
{ bool FlagNext = true;
  while (FlagNext)
  { switch (stG) // state groups
    { case 0U: // initial state group
      FlagNext = DeonYuli_Next0();
      break;
    case 1U: // xG generation group
      FlagNext = DeonYuli_Next1();
      break;
    case 2U: // change parameter group
      FlagNext = DeonYuli_Next2();
      break;
    } // switch
  } // while
  return xG; // created random number
}
//-----
bool DeonYuli_Next0()
{ bool FlagWhile0 = true; // parameter setting
  while (FlagWhile0) // st0 states running
  { switch (st0) // states switching

```

```

    { case 1U: // initial actions
      nA = 1U; // generation begins in a1
      a1s = 1U; // create twister 0 in a1
      a2s = 0U; // a2 while not used
      a1 = a1e; // end of interval a1
      a = a1; // current constant a
      a2 = a2b - 4U; // left from beginning of a2
      c = cb; // beginning of interval c
      st0 = 2U; // generation parameters
      break;
    case 2U: // for changed parameters
      xB = x0; // sequence beginning
      xR = xB; // end of pair xL, xR
      nT = 0U; // twister 0 number
      nW = 0U; // twister number in w
      nV = 0U; // initial value number
      stG = 1U; // xG group of generation
      st1 = 101U; // xG generation
      FlagWhile0 = false; // finish job
      break;
    } // switch
  } // while
  return true; // xG generation is necessary
}

//-----
bool DeonYuli_Next1()
{ bool FlagNext1 = false; // xG will be created
  bool FlagWhile1 = true; // looking for a twister
  while (FlagWhile1) // st1 states running
  { switch (st1) // states switching
    { case 101U: // congruential generation
      xL = xR; // beginning of pair
      xR = DeonYuli_Cong(xL); // pair xL, xR
      xG = xL; // generated number
      if (nV < N1) nV++; // next number
      else st1 = 102U;
      FlagWhile1 = false; // number is created
      break;
    case 102U: // for pair twister nW
      nW++; // pair twister number in w
      if (nW < w)
      { maskT = maskU; // elder 1 in twister mask
        for (int m = 1; m < nW; m++)
          maskT |= maskU >> m; // twister mask
        xL = xB; // beginning of twister
        xR = DeonYuli_Cong(xL); // pair xL, xR
        nV = 0U; // value number in twister nT
      }
    }
  }
}

```

```

        st1 = 103U;          // generate twister nT
    }
    else st1 = 104U;
    break;
case 103U:                  // twister generation
    xG = DeonYuli_TwistPair(); // pair twister
    xL = xR;                // beginning of the next pair
    xR = DeonYuli_Cong(xL); // napa xL, xR
    if (nV == N1) st1 = 102U;
    else nV++;              // next value number
    FlagWhile1 = false;    // number is created
    break;
case 104U:                  // nW twisters end in nT
    if (nT < N1)
    { nT++;                // nT number for twisters in nW
      xB = DeonYuli_Cong(xB);
      xR = xB;
      nW = 0U;            // twister number in w
      nV = 0U;            // value number in twister
      st1 = 101U;        // nT twister generation
    }
    else st1 = 105U;
    break;
case 105U:                  // constant changing
    stG = 2U;              // change parameter group
    st2 = 201U;            // parameters changing
    FlagWhile1 = false;    // group move out
    FlagNext1 = true;      // moving into group 2
    break;
} // switch
} // while
return FlagNext1;         // result of generation
}
//-----
bool DeonYuli_Next2()
{ bool FlagNext2 = true;    // to be changed
  bool FlagWhile2 = true;  // running flag
  while (FlagWhile2)
  { switch (st2)
    { case 201U:            // change parameter c
      c += 2U;             // next constant c
      if (c <= ce)
      { stG = 0U;          // initial action group
        st0 = 2U;         // current initial action
        FlagWhile2 = false; // work is over
        FlagNext2 = true; // move into group 0
      }
    }
  }
}

```

```

    else st2 = 202U;
    break;
case 202U:          // change interval for a
    c = cb;          // initial value c
    if (nA == 1U) nA = 2U; else nA = 1U;
    if (nA == 1U) st2 = 203U;    // interval a1
    else st2 = 204U;            // interval a2
    break;
case 203U:          // new value from a1
    a1 -= 4U;
    if (a1 < a1b)    // a1 is over
    { a1s = 2U;      // interval a1 is over
      st2 = 205U;   // states of intervals
      break;
    }
    a = a1;          // current constant a
    c = cb;          // beginning of constant c
    a1s = 1U;        // interval a1 is active
    stG = 0U;        // initial action group
    st0 = 2U;        // current initial actions
    FlagWhile2 = false; // work is over
    FlagNext2 = true; // move into group 0
    break;
case 204U:          // new value from a2
    a2 += 4U;
    if (a2 > a2e)    // a2 is finished
    { a2s = 2U;      // interval a2 is over
      st2 = 205U;   // interval states
      break;
    }
    a = a2;          // current constant a
    c = cb;          // beginning of constant c
    a2s = 1U;        // interval a2 is active
    stG = 0U;        // initial action group
    st0 = 2U;        // common initial generation
    FlagWhile2 = false; // work is over
    FlagNext2 = true; // move into group 0
    break;
case 205U:          // one of a1 or a2 is finished
    if (a2s != 2U) st2 = 204U;
    else if (a1s != 2U) st2 = 203U;
    else
    { stG = 0U;      // group 0
      st0 = 1U;     // common beginning
      FlagWhile2 = false; // work is over
      FlagNext2 = true; // move into group 0
    }
}

```

```

        break;
    }
}
return FlagNext2;           // work is over
}
//-----
uint DeonYuli_Cong(uint z)
{ return (a * z + c) & maskW; // the next number
}
//-----
uint DeonYuli_TwistPair()
{ uint g = (xR & maskT) >> (int)(w - nW); // elder
  return ((xL << (int)nW) & maskW) | g; // younger
}
//-----
public void Start()
{ N1 = 0xFFFFFFFF >> (32 - (int)w); // max-number
  maskW = 0xFFFFFFFF >> (32 - (int)w);
  maskU = 1U << ((int)w - 1); // elder bit mask
  maskT = maskU; // first twister bit
  DeonYuli_SetA(); // set a1 and a2 borders
  DeonYuli_SetC(); // set c borders
  x0 &= maskW;
  stG = 0U; // xG generation group
  st0 = 1U; // generator initialization
}
//-----
public void TimeStart()
{ x0 = (uint)DateTime.Now.Millisecond;
  Start(); // generator starts
}
//-----
public void SetW(int sw)
{ w = (uint)Math.Abs(sw); // number bit length
  if (w < 3U) w = 3U; // min-length
  else if (w > 32U) w = 32U; // max-length
  N1 = 0xFFFFFFFF >> (32 - (int)w); // max-number
  x0 = N1 / 7U; // sequence beginning
}
//-----
public void SetA(double sab, double sae)
{ abf = Math.Abs(sab);
  aef = Math.Abs(sae);
  if (abf > 1.0) abf = 1.0;
  if (aef > 1.0) aef = 1.0;
  if (abf > aef) aef = abf;
}

```

```

//-----
void DeonYuli_SetA()
{ a1b = (uint)(N1 * abf); // bottom edge for a1
  a1b = DeonYuli_PlusA(a1b); // beginning for a1
  a2e = (uint)(N1 * aef); // top edge for a2
  a2e = DeonYuli_MinusA(a2e); // ending for a2
  uint r = a2e - a1b;
  if (a1b >= a2e) // interval for a as a point
  { a1e = a1b; // a1 is a one point
    a2b = a1b; // interval a2 as a1
    a2e = a2b; // a2 is a one point
    return;
  }
  if (r == 4U) // one point a1 and a2
  { a1e = a1b; // a1 is one point
    a2b = a2e; // a2 is one point
    return;
  }
  if (r == 8U) // a1 has 2 points, a2 – one point
  { a1e = a1b + 4U; // ending of a1
    a2b = a2e; // beginning of a2
    return;
  }
  a1e = (a1b + a2e) / 2U; // middle for a
  a1e = DeonYuli_MinusA(a1e); // left from middle
  a2b = a1e + 4U; // right from middle
}
//-----
uint DeonYuli_PlusA(uint a)
{ if (a < 1U) { a = 1U; return a; }
  uint z = a; // bottom edge for a
  for (uint i = 0U; i < 3U; i++)
    if (a % 4U != 0U) a--; // uniform condition
    else break;
  a++; // true value for constant a
  if (a < z) a += 4U; // right from bottom edge
  if (a >= N1 - 1) a -= 4U; // left from top edge
  return a;
}
//-----
uint DeonYuli_MinusA(uint a)
{ if (a < 1U) { a = 1U; return a; }
  uint z = a; // bottom edge for a
  for (uint i = 0U; i < 3U; i++)
    if (a % 4U != 0U) a--; // uniform condition
    else break;
  a++; // true value for constant a
}

```

```

    if (a > z) a -= 4U;          // left from top edge
    return a;
}
//-----
public void SetC(double scb, double sce)
{ cbf = Math.Abs(scb);
  cef = Math.Abs(sce);
  if (cbf > 1.0) cbf = 1.0;
  if (cef > 1.0) cef = 1.0;
  if (cbf > cef) cef = cbf;
}
//-----
void DeonYuli_SetC()
{ cb = (uint)(N1 * cbf);      // bottom edge for c
  if (cb % 2U == 0U) cb += 1; // only odd value for c
  if (cb > N1) cb = N1;      // max-value
  ce = (uint)(N1 * cef);     // top edge for c
  if (ce % 2U == 0U) ce -= 1U; // only odd
  if (ce > N1 - 1) ce = N1;  // max-value
  if (cb > ce) ce = cb;
  c = cb;                    // beginning of congruential constant c
}
//-----
public void SetX0(double xs)
{ x0 = (uint)(N1 * Math.Abs(xs));
}
//=====
}
}
}

```

In class *cDeonYuliTwist32D* several variables are reserved. They can be tuned with the help of encapsulated functions. As a first example let's use the values for default settings to generate several random numbers having $w = 16$ bits length and belonging to interval $[0: 2^w - 1] = [0: 2^{16} - 1] = [0: 65535]$. The program code for this task is below. The names *P030401* and *cP030401* are chosen by chance.

```

using nsDeonYuliTwist32D;      // twister generator class
namespace P030401
{ class cP030401
  { static void Main(string[] args)
    { cDeonYuliTwist32D CT =
      new cDeonYuliTwist32D ();
      CT.Start();
      for ( int j = 0; j < 8; j++ )
      { uint z = CT.Next ();      // random number
        Console.Write ( "{0,7} ", z ); // monitor
      }
      Console.ReadKey ();        // result viewing
    }
  }
}

```

```

    }
  }
}

```

After execution the following result appears:

```
9362 36699 52924 2805 8774 14575 51504 13129
```

These random numbers are equal to the other ones under the same conditions but with help of twisting array in program *P020401* [Deon and Menyaev 2016].

Now let's look at another variant in which there is no possibility to use the congruential twisting array for computers having 32 bits of common data bus because of a lack of memory space for the program. The next program *P030402* can generate random numbers with a length of 32 bits using technology without congruential twisting array. Program names *P030402* and *cP030402* are chosen by chance.

```

using nsDeonYuliTwist32D;      // twister generator class
namespace P030402
{ class cP030402
  { static void Main(string[] args)
    { cDeonYuliTwist32D CT =
      new cDeonYuliTwist32D ();
      CT.SetW ( 32 );          // number bit length
      CT.Start();             // generator starts
      Console.WriteLine(
        "CT.x0 = {0} CT.a = {1} CT.c = {2}",
        CT.x0, CT.a, CT.c);
      for ( int j = 0; j < 8; j++ )
      { uint z = CT.Next ();   // random number
        Console.WriteLine ( "{0,10} ", z ); // monitor
      }
      Console.ReadKey();      // result viewing
    }
  }
}

```

The result of execution is the following:

```

CT.x0 = 613566756 CT.a = 5 CT.c = 429496729
613566756
3767299885
3711097170
85104163
2840182256
2787589065
706196094
2953448863

```

In the next code let's consider complete automatic tuning of parameters for

generator. Below is the program code, which allows tuning of the generator to different values of w , $x0$, $a1b$, $a2e$. As an example, the values are taken as: $w = 4$, $N = 2^w = 16$, $a1b = 1$, $a2e = 13$, $x0 = 1.0 \cdot (N - 1) = 15$. For each meaning of constant $a = 5, 9, 1, 13$ and constant $c = 1, 3, 5, 7, 9, 11, 13, 15$. Program names *P030403* and *cP030403* are chosen by chance.

```
using nsDeonYuliTwist32D;           // twisting generator
namespace P030403
{ class P030403
  { static void Main(string[] args)
    { cDeonYuliTwist32D CT =
      new cDeonYuliTwist32D();
      CT.SetW(4);                     // number bit length
      CT.SetA(0.0, 1.0);              // all of a
      CT.SetC(0.0, 1.0);              // all of c
      CT.SetX0(1.0);                 // sequence beginning
      CT.Start();                     // generator starts
      int N = (int)CT.N1 + 1;         // sequence length
      Console.WriteLine("w = {0} N = {1}", CT.w, N);
      Console.WriteLine("a1b = {0} a1e = {1}",
        CT.a1b, CT.a1e);
      Console.WriteLine("a2b = {0} a2e = {1}",
        CT.a2b, CT.a2e);
      Console.WriteLine("cb = {0} ce = {1}",
        CT.cb, CT.ce);
      Console.WriteLine("x0 = {0}", CT.x0);
      int k = 0;                       // sequence number
      int NN = 0;                       // quantity of random numbers
      for (int nw = 0; nw < CT.w; nw++)
        for (int nt = 0; nt < N; nt++)
          for (int na = 1; na <= 4; na++)
            for (int nc = 1; nc <= 8; nc++)
              {
                Console.Write("k={0,4} | ", ++k);
                for (int i = 0; i < N; i++)
                  {
                    Console.Write("{0,3}", CT.Next());
                    NN++;
                  }
                Console.WriteLine(" a={0,2} c={1,2}",
                  CT.a, CT.c);
                if (k % 250 == 0) Console.ReadKey();
              }
      Console.WriteLine("Finish");
      Console.WriteLine("NN = {0}", NN);
      Console.ReadKey();              // result viewing
    }
  }
}
```

}

The listing below is the result of program execution; it is presented with abridgements where dash lines are for skipped strings.

```
w = 4 N = 16
a1b = 1 a1e = 5
a2b = 9 a2e = 13
cb = 1 ce = 15
x0 = 15
k = 1 15 12 13 2 11 8 9 14 7 4 5 10 3 0 1 6 a = 5 c = 1
k = 2 15 9 10 5 7 1 3 12 14 8 11 4 6 0 2 13 a = 5 c = 1
-----
k = 1000 6 10 1 13 4 8 7 11 2 14 5 9 0 12 3 15 a = 9 c = 15
-----
k = 1230 9 6 5 2 0 15 12 11 8 7 4 3 1 14 13 10 a = 11 c = 7
-----
k = 1900 8 5 13 6 10 7 15 0 12 1 9 2 14 3 11 4 a = 13 c = 11
-----
k = 2048 7 9 4 10 1 11 6 12 3 13 0 14 5 15 2 8 a = 13 c = 15
Finish
NN = 32768
```

A total of $4 \cdot 16 \cdot 4 \cdot 8 = 2048$ sequences have been received. Since each sequence contains 16 non-repeatable random values, the total amount of generated numbers is $2048 \cdot 16 = 32768$. This result is equal to that one which was received with help of twisting array under the same conditions in program *P020403* [Deon and Menyayev 2016].

5 Discussion

Presented in the previous section, generator *nsDeonYuliTwist32D* is able to create random numbers having accidental bit length in diapason $3 \leq w \leq 32$. These numbers are distributed uniformly in the interval $[0: 2^w - 1]$. Among other things, the uniformity $U(w)$ for any number can be either unique $U(w) = 1$, or multivariate $U(w) > 1$. If all the complete sequences are generated, the uniformity $U(w)$ for all the numbers in all of them is the same. If single complete sequence is generated and it has 2^w numbers, that means each number may appear only once in this sequence, i.e. $U(w) = 1$. The difficulty, as it's mentioned above, is that computers with 32 bits of common data bus can't provide the array capable to contain $2^w = 2^{32}$ elements due to a lack of memory space for the computer program in this case. The external hard drive might help, but that solution is limited by slow processes. So, let's try to use RAM only.

Below is the program code in which the array of counters cX is used; it contains $ncX = 2^{28} = 268,435,456$ elements. Based on this array, the generator creates a single complete sequence with a length of $2^w = 2^{32} = 4,294,967,296$ elements. Each element is $w = 32$ bits long. Therefore, any generated random number x

belongs to interval $x \in [0:2^w - 1] = [0:2^{32} - 1] = [0:4,294,967,295]$. For each element in array cX let's count the amount of same values for which the index j is used. Because the generator creates all the numbers in complete sequence it means that counters in the beginning add up the quantity of elements $x \in [0:268,435,456]$. If the meaning of each element in cX is equal to 1, it means the generator at the initial iteration has created the random numbers from interval $[0:268,435,456]$ which may be found once only. This also corresponds to the statement that in a complete sequence there are 268,435,456 initial numbers from the interval of complete sequence $[0:4,294,967,296]$.

By organizing the program code so it performs $2^4 = 16$ iterations for 2^4 intervals; and with the total amount of elements being 2^{28} , which are then sorted out successively and fully within complete sequence $[0:2^{32} - 1]$, now it is possible to find out the answer to the question about unique properties of the numbers in a single complete sequence. This statement has to correspond with the uniform unique distribution $U(w) = 1$, which is provided by *nsDeonYuliTwist32D* generator for the initial complete twister 0. Next program names *P030511* and *cP030511* are chosen by chance.

```
using nsDeonYuliTwist32D; // twister generator class
namespace P030511
{ class cP030511
  { static void Main ( string[] args )
    { cDeonYuliTwist32D CT =
      new cDeonYuliTwist32D();
      CT.SetW ( 32 ); // set a number bit length
      CT.Start (); // generator starts
      uint w = CT.w; // number bit length
      uint N1 = CT.N1; // max-number
      Console.WriteLine ( "w = {0} N1 = {1}", w, N1 );
      uint N28_1 = 0xFFFFFFFF; // work max
      uint N28 = N28_1 + 1; // work interval length
      Console.WriteLine ( "N28_1 = {0:X} N28 = {1}",
        N28_1, N28 );
      uint[] cX = new uint[N28]; // repeating counter
      uint Total1 = 0; // total quantity of single numbers
      uint q1 = 0U; // quantity of one time numbers
      uint q2 = 0U; // quantity of two times numbers
      uint cXD = N28_1; // last index in cX
      uint cXB = 0U; // beginning of interval
      uint cXE = cXB + cXD; // ending of interval
      Console.WriteLine ( "m cXB cXE q1 q2");
      for ( uint m = 1U; m <= 16U; m++ ) //with intervals
      { Console.Write ( "{0,2}", m );
        Console.Write ( " {0,10} {1,10}", cXB, cXE);
        for ( uint i = 0U; i <= cXD; i++ ) cX[i] = 0U;
        uint n = 0U; // number counter inside interval
        while (true)
```

```

{ uint x = CT.Next();          // random number
  if (cXB <= x && x <= cXE) cX[x - cXB]++;
  if ( n == N1 ) break;       // end of interval
  n++;                          // quantity of created numbers
}
q1 = 0U;                        // quantity of one time numbers
q2 = 0U;                        // quantity of two times numbers
for (uint i = 0; i < N28; i++)
  if (cX[i] == 1) q1++;        // one time numbers
  else if (cX[i] == 2) q2++;   // two times numbers
Console.WriteLine(" {0} {1}", q1, q2);
if (m == 16) break;
Total1 += q1;                  // total of one time numbers
cXB = cXE + 1;                 // the next interval
cXE = cXB + cXD;
}
Total1 = (q1 - 1) + Total1;
Console.WriteLine("Total = {0} + 1", Total1);
Console.ReadKey();             // result viewing
}
}
}
}

```

After the program execution the listing below appears on monitor.

```

w = 32 N1 = 4294967295
N28_1 = FFFFFFFF N28 = 268435456
m      cXB      cXE      q1      q2
1          0      268435455 268435456 0
2  268435456  536870911 268435456 0
3  536870912  805306367 268435456 0
4  805306368 1073741823 268435456 0
5 1073741824 1342177279 268435456 0
6 1342177280 1610612735 268435456 0
7 1610612736 1879048191 268435456 0
8 1879048192 2147483647 268435456 0
9 2147483648 2415919103 268435456 0
10 2415919104 2684354559 268435456 0
11 2684354560 2952790015 268435456 0
12 2952790016 3221225471 268435456 0
13 3221225472 3489660927 268435456 0
14 3489660928 3758096383 268435456 0
15 3758096384 4026531839 268435456 0
16 4026531840 4294967295 268435456 0
Total1 = 4294967295 + 1

```

These received results show that in the general interval of generation $[0: 2^{32} - 1]$ all subintervals with length of 2^{28} numbers are passed 16 times. Parameters cXB and

cXE point out the beginning and the ending of each subinterval. Values for counters $q1$, which are for momentary observation of random numbers, are equal for all the subintervals and was determined as 268435456. That is equal to the subinterval length $2^{28} = 268,436,456$ which means each random number was definitely observed once. The values $q2 = 0$ demonstrate that no unique number is generated twice or more times. It means the generator indeed exhibits properties of uniform generation of random numbers.

The total amount of bits $N_b(w, N)$ for the sequence consisting in N numbers, with them being w bits long, may be found as:

$$N_b(w, N) = w \cdot N. \quad (4)$$

Let's consider the proposed generator *nsDeonYuliTwist32D* in comparison with the well-known generator MT19937 [Matsumoto and Nishimura 1998], which uses a congruential twisting array having 624 elements, and each element is 32 bits long. In this case the bit length of sequence is the following: $MT_b(w, N) = MT_b(32, 624) = 32 \cdot 624 - 31 = 19968 - 31 = 19937$. Diminution of value 31 is because the generator MT19937 doesn't take into account the circle of needless bits. In MT19937 only the transformation of the next congruential twisting number with a length of 32 bits happens. That means, a recurrence interval in this case is $R_{MT19937} = 2^{19937} - 1$.

In the generator *nsDeonYuliTwist32D* considered here, the maximal sequences are created with the values having length of 32 bits. In this case the bit length of sequence is determined as follows: $N_b(w, N) = N_b(32, 2^{32}) = 32 \cdot 4294967296 = 2^{37} = 137,484,953,472$. In turn, a recurrence interval is defined as $R_{nsDeonYuliTwist32D} = 2^{2^{37}} - 1$. This value is extremely big, and in general it means that potency (or computational capability) of generator *nsDeonYuliTwist32D* is in excess of generator MT19937 due to $R_{nsDeonYuliTwist32D} \gg R_{MT19937}$.

The complete twister consists of the initial congruential sequence and the sequences which are received by single circular bit shifts $N_t = w \cdot N - 1$ times. Thus, total amount $N_T(w, N_t)$ of sequences of complete twister contains the sum of single congruential sequence, i.e. twister 0, and all other twisting sequences:

$$N_T(w, N_t) = 1 + N_t = 1 + (w \cdot N - 1) = w \cdot N = w \cdot 2^w. \quad (5)$$

From the definitions of $N_T(w, N_t)$ and $N_b(w, N)$ it follows that for complete sequences they are equal $N_T(w, N_t) = N_b(w, N)$. For the case of no twisters the equation is $N_T(w, N_t = 0) = 1 + 0 = 1$, i.e. only a single complete congruential sequence is generated. Each number in it is presented once, and level of uniformity or repentances in this case is $U_T(w, N_t = 0) = 1$.

The previous result confirms the fact that the generation of 2^w numbers creates single complete congruential sequence having a momentary uniform distribution of random numbers $U_T(w, N_t = 0) = 1$. However, in complete twister there is a total amount of $N_T(w, N_t) = w \cdot N = w \cdot 2^w$ sequences. In this case the level of uniformity is equal to the amount of twisting sequences because each number in single complete sequence is presented once:

$$U_T(w, N_t) = N_T(w, N_t) = w \cdot N = w \cdot 2^w. \quad (6)$$

Let's take the benefits from the previous program *P030511* in which the array of

counters having $2^{28} = 268,435,456$ elements was used. Because the quantity of twisters is equal to the amount of unique complete sequences, that means a uniformity of distribution is defined by the level of $U_T(w = 28, N_t) = N_T(w = 28, N_t) = w \cdot 2^w = 28 \cdot 2^{28} = 7,516,192,768$. However, this value is bigger than maximum for 32 bits number which is $2^{32} - 1 = 4,294,967,295$.

To define a permissible amount of bits w , it is required to take into consideration the maximal value of repentances for counter, i.e. solving the equation $w \cdot 2^w = 2^{32}$ is needed. By using binary logarithm it is obvious that for $w \leq 32$ this equation has no integer number solution. Thus, the testing of complete twister for the single pair of congruential constants a and c should be done for the numbers having $w = 27$ bit length. In this case the uniformity is $U_T(w = 27, N_t) = N_T(w = 27, N_t) = w \cdot 2^w = 27 \cdot 2^{27} = 3,623,876,656$ and it complies with a range of values $2^{31} < U_T(w = 27, N_t + 1) < 2^{32}$.

Below is the program code which performs the complete generation of twisting sequences for the random numbers having $w = 12$ bit length. Each random number has to be appeared the same amount of times as the twisting sequences because in each sequence it may be found once. Program names *P030512* and *cP030512* are chosen by chance.

```
using nsDeonYuliTwist32D;      // twister generator class
namespace P030512
{ class cP030512
  { static void Main(string[] args)
    { cDeonYuliTwist32D CT =
      new cDeonYuliTwist32D();
      CT.SetW ( 12 );          // set a number bit length
      CT.SetA ( 0.3, 0.3 );   // single constant a
      CT.SetC ( 0.2, 0.2 );   // single constant c
      CT.Start ();           // generator starts
      uint w = CT.w;         // number bit length
      uint N = CT.N1 + 1;    // sequence length
      Console.WriteLine ( "w = {0} N = {1}", w, N );
      uint[] cX = new uint[N]; // repeating counter
      for ( uint i = 0U; i < N; i++ ) cX[i] = 0U;
      int mStart = DateTime.Now.Minute;
      int sStart = DateTime.Now.Second;
      for ( uint nW = 0U; nW < w; nW++ ) // twisters
      {
//      Console.WriteLine ( "nW = {0}", nW );
        for ( uint nT = 0U; nT < N; nT++ ) // twisters
          for ( uint i = 0U; i < N; i++ )
            { uint x = CT.Next (); // random numbers
              cX[x]++; // number x counter
            }
      }
      int sFinish = DateTime.Now.Second;
      int mFinish = DateTime.Now.Minute;
    }
  }
}
```

```

Console.WriteLine(
    "mStart = {0,2} sStart = {1,2}",
    mStart, sStart);
Console.WriteLine (
    "mFinish = {0,2} sFinish = {1,2}",
    mFinish, sFinish);
uint nwN = w * N; // quantity of twisters
Console.WriteLine ( "nwN = {0}", nwN );
uint countX = 0;
for ( uint i = 0; i < N; i++ )
    if ( cX[i] == nwN ) countX++; // one time
Console.WriteLine ( "countX = {0}", countX );
Console.ReadKey (); // result viewing
}
}
}

```

After execution the result appears as the following:

```

w = 12 N = 4096
mStart = 8 sStart = 1
mFinish = 8 sFinish = 16
nwN = 49152
countX = 4096

```

This listing suggests that length of random numbers is 12 bits; each complete sequence contains 4096 random numbers; duration of generation lasts $T_s(w = 12) = 15$ seconds; a total of 49152 complete twisting sequences are created, and that is maximum of unique sequences in which it is possible to generate for the single pair of constants a and c . Therefore, all 4096 numbers have the same amount of repentances with a level of distribution uniformity $U_T(w, w \cdot N_t) = w \cdot N = 12 \cdot 4096 = 49152$. And they cover uniformly the interval of random numbers $x \in [0: 2^w - 1] = [0: 4095]$.

Besides this, the next step is to estimate the time period required for generation of single number. Because each complete sequence contains $N = 2^w$ random numbers, that means a total amount $N_s(w, N)$ of them could be found as multiplication of all the numbers in single sequence by amount of twisting sequences:

$$N_s(w, N) = N \cdot N_T(w, w \cdot N_t) = N \cdot w \cdot N = 2^w \cdot w \cdot 2^w = w \cdot 2^{2w}. \quad (7)$$

For the previous example it is $N_s(w, N) = w \cdot 2^{2w} = 12 \cdot 2^{2 \cdot 12} = 12 \cdot 16,777,216 = 201,326,592$ of random values. So, the generation time for the single random number is:

$$t_1 = \frac{T_s(w)}{N_s(w, N)}. \quad (8)$$

Substituting into this formula the values from the previous example, the generation time can be estimated as $15/201,326,592 = 0.0000000745s = 0.0745\mu s$. In Table

1 there are results of generation of the random numbers having different bit length w .

w	$N = 2^w$	$N_s = w \cdot 2^{2w}$	T_s	$t_1 \cdot 10^{-6}$ (μs)
12	4,096	201,326,592	15''	0.0745
13	8,192	872,415,232	1'04''	0.0734
14	16,384	3,758,096,384	4'36''	0,0734
15	32768	16,106,127,360	19'42''	0,0734
16	65,536	68,719,476,736	1h24'04''	0,0734
17	131,072	292,057,776,128	5h57'17''	0,0734
18	264,144	1,263,950,581,248	25h13'12''	0,0734
19	524,288	5,222,680,231,936	106h29'05''	0,0734
20	1,048,576	21,990,232,555,520	448h21'23''	0,0734

Table 1: Generation time of complete twister for different bit length

The calculations considered above are directed to single pair of congruential constants a and c , but *nsDeonYuliTwist32D* generator allows tuning of the generation for different combinations of pairs a and c . For the complete sequences the constant a has to satisfy the condition $(a - 1) \bmod 4 = 0$. Due to $a \in [1, N] = [1: 2^w - 1]$, the number of different values N_a is defined as:

$$N_a = \frac{N}{4} = \frac{2^w}{2^2} = 2^{w-2}. \quad (9)$$

When generating complete sequences the value of constant c has to be odd. Therefore, the total number of values for c is defined as:

$$N_c = \frac{N}{2} = \frac{2^w}{2^1} = 2^{w-1}. \quad (10)$$

Thus, last two formulas allow defining the total number N_{ac} of pairs of a and c :

$$N_{ac} = N_a \cdot N_c = 2^{w-2} \cdot 2^{w-1} = 2^{2w-3}. \quad (11)$$

Taking into consideration the quantity of generations in all possible cases for sequences of twisters and congruential constants, the final estimation $N_T(w, N_{ac})$ of amount of created non-repeatable twisting complete sequences looks like:

$$N_T(w, N_{ac}) = N_T \cdot N_{ac} = w 2^{2w} \cdot 2^{2w-3} = w \cdot 2^{4w-3}. \quad (12)$$

Because each sequence contains unique non-repeatable whole numbers it means the absolute level of uniform distribution coincides with a total amount of twisters:

$$U_T(w, N_{ac}) = N_T(w, N_{ac}) = w \cdot 2^{4w-3}. \quad (13)$$

At the same time, amount of random numbers $N_s(w, N_{ac})$ having w bit length is:

$$N_s(w, N_{ac}) = N \cdot N_T(w, N_{ac}) = 2^w \cdot w \cdot 2^{4w-3} = w \cdot 2^{5w-3}. \quad (14)$$

So, if random values with a length of 32 bits are created, the repeated generation

of complete twisting sequence will occur after generation of $N_s(w = 32, N_{ac}) = 32 \cdot 2^{5 \cdot 32 - 3} = 2^5 \cdot 2^{157} = 2^{162}$ numbers. This will require plenty of time for the computers having generation time period for the single number as $0.0734 \mu\text{s}$.

We have demonstrated that object twisting generator *nsDeonYuliTwist32D* is capable to create sufficiently long sequences of random numbers having absolute level of uniform distribution. More importantly, this generator does not use an additional array for storing of transitional congruential twisting sequences, and thus it takes the minimum possible memory of computer RAM.

6 Conclusion

Analysis of sources shows that algorithms of modern twisting generators are mainly based on the initial congruential array which is limited by the size. This kind of technology uses a bit shifting inside the array and resulted in the appearance of new twisting sequences. However, the problem is that the limited size of arrays may be unacceptable for some practical implementations. Increasing the length of sequences requires an enlarging of amount of elements in an array. It has been proven previously that only complete sequences satisfy the properties of absolute uniformity, but their longitude depends on a bit length of generated random numbers. If the bit length is very large it will limit the available memory to place the application program. To overcome this kind of limitation, in this paper we have proposed an algorithm in which no congruential twisting array is used. This solution allows generation of very large sequences. In this case they are restricted by permissible bit length of numbers to be processed directly by the commands of the computer processor. Presented results of testing confirm these statements and demonstrate the proved uniform distribution of generated numbers. The using of an automatic tuning of congruential parameters allows a controlled level of repetition for generating uniform distribution. In general, all the aspects disclosed herein may be used for a large number of application tasks.

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